

Hidden Heritage of Kaimur Hills: An Exploration Beyond the Buddhist Circuit in Kaimur & Rohtas, Bihar

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Abstract

This paper explores the hidden heritage of Kaimur Hills, a region rich in ancient temples, forts, and rock art spanning various dynasties and periods. It highlights the challenges of documenting and preserving these sites due to past Conflict activity and the region's complex geography. The study underscores the potential of Kaimur Hills to emerge as a prime tourism destination, offering a unique mix of eco-tourism, wildlife, history, and heritage creating a comprehensive experience that blends natural beauty with cultural significance. These largely forgotten treasures, though neglected for years, hold immense potential to be rediscovered and celebrated. The paper also examines recent efforts to bring Kaimur Hills into the spotlight, emphasizing the need for conservation to safeguard its unique historical and cultural landscape, while expanding the understanding of its past, present, and future potential.

Keywords: Ancient Temples, Bihar, Bodh Gaya, Cultural Conservation, Hidden Heritage, Kaimur Hills, Rohtas, Rohtasgarh Fort, Rock Art, Sarnath, Sher Shah Suri, Vindhya Range

Introduction

Bihar, renowned for its Buddhist and Jain heritage, has been shaped by significant empires such as those led by Ashoka the Great, Chandragupta Maurya, and Sher Shah Suri. As the birthplace of Lord Buddha and Lord Mahavira, it holds immense spiritual and cultural value. However, beyond

the prominent Buddhist sites, the Kaimur Hills (see [Figure 1](#)) part of the Vindhya Range spanning Kaimur and Rohtas districts harbour lesser-known but profoundly significant heritage, including aspects of Buddhism.

This paper aims to shed light on these hidden treasures, offering a comprehensive exploration of the Kaimur Hills' historical and cultural importance within the broader Buddhist context. By documenting the current status of these remarkable yet underappreciated sites, the study seeks to reveal their significant potential for historical marvel. The ultimate goal is to ensure that the Kaimur Hills, with their remarkable but currently overshadowed heritage, can one day receive the recognition and acclaim they truly deserve.

Figure 1. Kaimur Hill: Easternmost Part of the Vindhya Range in Kaimur and Rohtas Districts, Bihar.

Beyond the Buddhist Circuit

While Bihar's Buddhist heritage attracts global attention, the Kaimur Hills offer a broader perspective on the region's historical and cultural depth. This paper delves into the less explored aspects of Kaimur heritage, including its ancient temples, forts, rock art, and natural wonders. Positioned between the prominent Buddhist centres of Sarnath and Bodh Gaya, the Kaimur Hills are often overshadowed by these renowned locations. Nevertheless, this area, encompassing Kaimur and Rohtas districts, is rich in historical and cultural assets that contribute to its unique heritage, extending far beyond the well-known Buddhist sites.

Historical and Geographical Context

Formation and Division

The Kaimur Hills, located in southwestern Bihar, were once part of the larger Rohtas district. In 1991, the Rohtas district was bifurcated to create the Kaimur district, with Bhabua as its headquarters. The district is bordered by Buxar and Ghazipur (Uttar Pradesh) to the north, Garhwa (Jharkhand) to the south, and Chandauli and Mirzapur (Uttar Pradesh) to the west, with Rohtas to the east. (Choudhary, 1966)

Figure 2. Kaimur Hill view and water reservoir with river safari at Karamchat Dam. (Photo credit: Kushwaha. D)

Environmental and Archaeological Significance

The Kaimur Hills (see [Error! Reference source not found.](#)) are celebrated for their rich natural beauty and archaeological potential. The region's landscape is characterized by dense jungles, gorges, and waterfalls. The Vindhyan ranges, stretching from Katangi in Madhya Pradesh to Sasaram ([Oldham, 1856](#)) in Bihar, have been a haven for human activities since prehistoric times. Over 500 rock shelters, many adorned with ancient paintings, have been discovered in this area, revealing a continuous human presence spanning millennia.

The Heritage of Kaimur and Rohtas

Kaimur District

Established on March 17, 1991, from Rohtas district, Kaimur district, with Bhabua as its headquarters, has a deep-rooted history that extends beyond its formal establishment. The region was part of Ghazipur district until 1764 and later belonged to the Chainpur Estate ([O'Malley, 1906](#)) until 1837. The district is divided into two sub-divisions: Bhabua and Mohania, with a total of eleven blocks. Covering an area of 3,332 Sq. km ([India, 2011](#)), Kaimur historical significance is highlighted by evidence of human habitation dating back approximately 20,000 years, as depicted in the rock paintings of Lehda forest. The recent discovery of Pala sculptures in Baidyanath village in June 2012 further emphasizes the district's rich heritage. Despite its historical and cultural importance, Kaimur is currently part of the Red Corridor, a region affected by Left-Wing Extremism (LWE).

Rohtas District

Created in 1972 from the former Shahabad district, Rohtas district, with Sasaram as its headquarters, has a storied past that stretches back centuries. The district is divided into three sub-divisions: Sasaram, Dehri, and Bikramganj, with a total of 19 blocks. Covering an area of 3,847.82 Sq. km, this region was a key part of the Magadh Empire from the 6th century BCE to the 5th century CE and Mauryans conquests ([Census of India, 2011](#)) of this district in the 7th century CE. Rohtas played a crucial role during the reigns of notable rulers such as Ashoka and Harsha and later came under Afghan and Mughal rule. Significant historical events include Sher Shah Suri's rise to power and Raja Chait Singh's revolt against the British. The district also witnessed

resistance during the 1857 rebellion, led by Kunwar Singh. Rohtas is also currently part of the Red Corridor, a region affected by Left-Wing Extremism (LWE).

Challenges and Resilience: The Conflict Legacy of Kaimur Hills

The Kaimur Hills and Rohtas district have long been part of conflict zones, experiencing significant challenges due to Left-Wing Extremism (LWE). The region was heavily impacted by Naxal activities, which posed serious threats to law and order. Central forces were deployed on a permanent basis to maintain control, alongside local police and administration. The difficult terrain, characterized by dense forests, mountains, waterfalls, and its connection to the jungles of Jharkhand, made securing the area especially challenging.

Figure 3. Security forces engaged during Operation Vidhwansh and camping at Rohtasgarh Fort. (Photo Credit: Vaibhav. V)

By 2008 to 2010, Operation Vidhwansh (Vaibhav, 2013) had played a crucial role in addressing these security issues, leading to a significant reduction in extremist activities. This operation (see Figure 3) aimed to restore peace and protect the heritage of the Kaimur Hills. Today, while the region is under government control, its past struggles are part of its narrative. The hills, once beset by conflict, are now gradually revealing their natural beauty and historical richness, offering opportunities for exploration and appreciation.

The Enigmatic Kaimur Hills

Cultural and Historical Significance

The Kaimur Hills are a veritable repository of historical and cultural treasures, offering a rich array of ancient Hindu temples (O'Malley, 1906) and Afghan-era architecture. These hills are distinguished by notable structures from the Sher Shah Suri period, including grand forts, mausoleums, tombs, and mosques that reflect the architectural prowess and cultural influences of the era. The ancient Hindu temples scattered across the region stand as enduring symbols of long-standing religious traditions, with intricate designs that provide a glimpse into the area's historical spirituality and artistic achievements. These temples, with their elaborate carvings and unique architectural styles, reveal the deep religious and artistic heritage of the region.

Despite their significant historical and cultural value, many of these sites remain relatively underexplored. Historical documents and inscriptions offer valuable insights into the Kaimur Hills' strategic and cultural importance, revealing their influential role in the broader historical landscape of medieval India. These documents (Choudhary, 1966) highlight the region's strategic significance and its role as a centre of cultural and political activity.

Significant Prehistoric Sites and Early Settlements in the Kaimur Hills

The Kaimur Hills, spanning both Kaimur and Rohtas districts in Southwestern Bihar, India, are renowned for their deep historical and archaeological significance, with evidence of human activity extending back to before 10,000 BCE. This region is distinguished by over 500 prehistoric rock shelters adorned with paintings depicting hunting scenes, animals, and abstract symbols. These ancient artworks provide valuable insights into the daily lives, environmental interactions, and ritual practices of early societies, reflecting the cultural and artistic evolution of prehistoric times.

A landmark exploration during 1994-95, led by Anand Kumar and the Directorate of Archaeology, Bihar, under Prakash Charan Prasad, uncovered (Prasad, 2001) over a dozen new rock painting sites, including Mokwas, Patesar, and Badap Gaura Hill. Significant rock art sites within the Kaimur Hills are located in Adhaura, Bhagwanpur, Chand, and Rampur blocks of the Kaimur district, as well as Sasaram, Tilauthu, Rohtas, and Nauhatta blocks of the Rohtas district.

In addition to rock art, notable archaeological finds include a Neolithic settlement at Chirand (Tiwari S. K., 2014) and artifacts from the Senubar site, dating to 2200–1950 BCE and 1950–1300 BCE, respectively. The artistic traditions of the Kaimur Hills exhibit striking similarities to those found in Mirzapur, Uttar Pradesh, revealing regional artistic connections within the Vindhya Range.

Notable Prehistoric Sites Include:

1. Rock Art & Inscription, Bhagwanpur, Kaimur Hill

Bhagwanpur, located 12 km from Bhabua City in Kaimur district, is noted for its intricate rock art and inscriptions that offer profound insights into prehistoric life. The site is renowned for its detailed rock art, depicting human figures, animals, and abstract symbols that reflect daily life, social structures, and possibly ritualistic practices of ancient communities.

Figure 4. General view and detailed pictographs of shelter wall and ceiling, Bhagwanpur Block, Kaimur (Photo Credit: Tiwari S.K)

The inscriptions found at Bhagwanpur, (see [Figure 4](#)) potentially in early scripts, provide critical context for interpreting the rock art. They highlight the evolution of early literacy and record-keeping practices in the region. Together, these elements help researchers trace the evolution of writing and its integration with rock art (Tiwari S. K., 2014), enhancing our understanding of ancient artistic and communicative practices.

Here are a few sites showcasing similar historical significance:

1.1 Badki Goriya Hill, Mokalikhoh

Located approximately 20 km west of the Kaimur district headquarter and 6 km southwest of Bhagwanpur block (24° 56' 47.49" N, 83° 35' 39.02" E), in the Mokalikhoh valley, this site features caves with rock art predominantly in red ochre. The artwork depicts animals such as rhinos, wild pigs, deer, and a crocodile-like creature. Engravings and gauging patterns on cave floors indicate early human artistic expressions and record-keeping practices.

1.2 Mundeshwari Hill (Pravara Hill)

Situated about 12 km west of Bhabua police station in Ramgarh village, Bhagwanpur block (24° 58' 59.08" N, 83° 33' 49.67" E), this site is renowned for the Mundeshwari Devi temple, notable for its unique rectangular design in North India. The site also contains rock art with inscriptions in various scripts, including Kushana, Gupta, and Nagari. Although it lacks ancient pictographs, modern paintings and inscriptions offer valuable historical and chronological insights.

1.3 Mokari Khoh Hill, Krishnapur Village

Located near right side of river Suara near Krishnapur village, Bhagwanpur block (24° 55' 08.14" N, 83° 35' 41.54" E), this site features Nagari script inscriptions on a boulder, alongside later-period engravings depicting human figures and animals. These inscriptions and figures provide valuable information about the region's historical and cultural development.

1.4 Gausgir Baba Ka Ashram

Situated on Ghamha hill, 3 km southwest of the Mundeshwari temple, Bhagwanpur block (24° 57' 11.66" N, 83° 30' 19.74" E), this religious site features pictographs of hunting scenes with detailed representations of animals and weapons. The site has been impacted by visitor rituals, including the application of oil and colourful papers over the pictographs. Hematite, used in painting the rock art, is abundant in the area.

2. Rock Art & Inscriptions, Adhaura, Kaimur Hill

Adhaura, located 55 km from Bhabua City in Kaimur district, is renowned for its extensive rock art, offering valuable historical and cultural insights. The region features prominent sites such as

Dugha, Hathiadag, Sarodag, Mahakol Mouza, Darihara, Chikta (Bechiragi), Turidag, Gudri, Chaya, Badap Gaura Hill, Rauta, and Kokhargada, and several (Tiwari S. K., 2019) other sites.

These sites are distinguished by their diverse rock art motifs that document various aspects of ancient life. The rock art vividly portrays animals, human figures, and environmental elements, reflecting daily activities and cultural symbols of the past. Together, these elements help researchers trace the evolution of artistic expression in the region, enhancing our understanding of ancient communicative practices.

Here are a few sites showcasing similar historical significance:

2.1 Dariyawa Maan, Tala

Located near Tala village in the Adhaura (Tiwari S. S., 2016) Block (24° 46' 27" N, 83° 33' 7" E), Dariyawa Maan is a significant rock shelter with vivid red ochre paintings. The artwork depicts various animals and human figures and is accompanied by a nearby microlithic factory for tool production from the Mesolithic era. The visibility of the paintings is currently affected by natural weathering and the presence of wasps.

2.2 Channava Mana, Gudri

Situated south of Gudri village in the Adhaura Block (24° 49' 36" N, 83° 31' 38" E), Channava Mana is a rock shelter featuring notable red paintings illustrating domestic animals such as bulls and cows, along with human figures. These Neolithic-era artworks, dating back to around 2000 BC, provide insights into early agricultural and pastoral life.

2.3 Asnahar Duhi Maan, Karar

Found east of Telhar Bus Stand in the Adhaura Block (24° 49' 58" N, 83° 32' 33" E), Asnahar Duhi Maan features medieval frescoes portraying a variety of human and animal figures. The site includes paintings of monkeys and dogs, as well as scenes of hunting and boating. The artwork, dating back to the early medieval period, is located on a hill with a rock shelter offering views of the surrounding landscape.

3. Rock Art, Shelters & Inscription, Sasaram (Rohtas), Kaimur Hill

Figure 5. Pictographs of Hathiya Man, Elephant, Amjhar Man, and Barahmasiya Man in Rohtas, Sasaram. (Photo credit: Tiwari S. S)

Sasaram, the headquarters and Sadar block of Rohtas district, is renowned for its significant rock shelters, which provide invaluable historical and cultural insights. The region (Tiwari S. K., 2019) includes several notable sites, such as Ashikpur (Chandan Shaheed) hill, Dhaudarh hill, Burhi Khoh hill, Goria-Bhokhrava, Domkhwa, Golka, Chamsia, Gram Dhaudad, Satgharwa, Bahalki, Chowghatia Maan, Murghat Ghati, Ghorghat Valley, Hathiya, Barhamsia, Amjhar, and several other sites. These shelters are distinguished by their diverse rock paintings (see [Error! Reference source not found.](#)) and engravings, depicting animals, human figures, and geometric patterns that reflect ancient life and cultural symbols.

Excavations at nearby sites like Senuar and Sakas (Bates, 2024) have revealed Neolithic and Chalcolithic artifacts, enriching our understanding of the region's Stone Age heritage and its artistic evolution. This rich diversity of art and artifacts helps trace the evolution of artistic expression and enhances our understanding of ancient communicative practices.

Here are a few sites (Tiwari S. S., 2021) showcasing similar historical significance:

3.1 Barhamsiya Maan:

The Barhamsiya Maan rock paintings, located in the Barhamsiya (24° 56' 22.82 "N, 84° 2' 55.95" E), region of the Kaimur Hills, Sasaram, Rohtas are a compelling example of early human artistic endeavors. These paintings provide a vivid depiction of hunting scenes, daily activities, and the natural environment of early human societies. The use of natural pigments and the simplicity of the artwork reflect the early stages of artistic expression and communication. These paintings are invaluable for understanding the cultural and environmental context in which they were created, offering insights into the lifestyle and artistic practices of prehistoric communities.

3.2 Ghorghat Valley Maan:

The Ghorghat Valley rock paintings, located in the Ghorghat Valley, (24° 48' 2.82" N, 83° 58' 38.07" E), Sasaram, Rohtas. This rock shelter features a group of small human figures advancing toward an animal, with its skeleton visible, reflecting early human hunting activities. The artwork includes depictions of animals and abstract symbols, offering insights into how prehistoric humans interacted with their environment and represented their daily lives and beliefs. These paintings highlight the artistic skills and cultural expressions of ancient people and are essential for understanding the role of animals in their culture and the evolution of artistic techniques over time.

3.3. Amjhar Maan:

The Amjhar Maan rock shelter is located near Bhokharwa village in Sivasagar (24° 47' 32.60 " N, 83° 57' 16" E), Sasaram. This site features a range of rock paintings, including scenes of men on horses, elephants, and geometric patterns. The central section illustrates the Mahabharata war with Arjuna and Krishna in a chariot and various animals. Additional artworks include prominent anthropomorphic figures and dynamic hunting scenes. These paintings reflect a progression in artistic styles and themes, offering insights into the evolution of artistic techniques and cultural practices in the region.

3.4 Petroglyph of Hathiya Maan:

The petroglyphs at Hathiya Maan, located in Hathiyaamaan (24° 56' 36.23" N, 84° 02' 15.55" E), Sasaram, Rohtas showcase intricate carvings that provide valuable insights into ancient symbolism and artistic expression. This rock shelter features detailed motifs, including five elephants and figures related to ancient games, which may hold religious or ceremonial significance. Unlike rock paintings, these petroglyphs are often more complex and detailed, revealing how ancient societies

used art to express and communicate their beliefs and practices, as well as their symbolic and ritualistic aspects of prehistoric life.

3.5 Phulwariya Inscription:

The Phulwariya Inscription is located in Phulwariya village, (24° 46' 54" N, 83° 48' 30" E), situated on a forested hilltop approximately 1500 feet high in Tilothu block, Rohtas district. This inscription, written by Pratap Dhaval Dev of the Khayarwal dynasty on 27 March 1169 AD (Vaishakh month of Vikram Samvat 1225), is a significant artifact for studying early written communication. The inscription, in early Nagari script and Sanskrit, provides crucial evidence for the development of writing systems in ancient India. It reveals the complete genealogy of the Khayarwal dynasty and details administrative, religious, and cultural practices of the time, including the construction of a road and steps on the river and mountain. The Phulwariya Inscription highlights the role of writing in organizing and recording societal information, reflecting the administrative and cultural importance of the period.

3.6 Megalithic Tombs, Kaimur Hill:

The megalithic tombs on Kaimur Hill, Rohtas, including the 'Sangora tombs' and 'Stone pillars' (Menhirs) dating from 1500 BC to 500 BC, offer crucial insights into ancient burial practices and societal organization. Notable among these is Chhotaki Chati, which extends between 24°37'48" to 24°37'55.4" north latitude and 83°56'2.4" to 83°56'24" east longitude. It features distinctive megalithic structures like cairn circles and two stone pillars, each standing 90 cm tall with diameters of 1.38 meters and 1.50 meters. The site highlights the rich megalithic tradition of the area, showcasing various 'Sangora Samadhis' and stone pillars across Kaimur Hills. This evidence underscores the continuity of megalithic traditions among local tribes, including Nishad-vanshi and Dravidian-origin Oraon, marking Kaimur Hill as a significant site in Indian archaeology.

3.7 Ashokan Miniature Inscription on Chandan Shahid Hill:

The 3rd century BCE Ashokan miniature inscription on Chandan Shahid Hill, (24° 56' 29.5" N 84° 02' 17.7" E), Sasaram, Rohtas, is a significant artifact from Emperor Ashoka's reign (272-232 BC). Written in Brahmi script on the northern wall of a cave about 30 feet below the hilltop, this inscription reflects Ashoka's efforts to spread his Dhamma and provides insights into his policies and the development of writing systems. Ashoka's inscriptions, primarily in Prakrit and Brahmi script, were intended to disseminate his messages widely, ensuring broad public access. The

inscription was preserved in 1917 by the Archaeological Conservation Department of India and later notified as a protected monument in 2008.

Forts in Kaimur Hill

The Kaimur Hills are distinguished by historic forts from the era of Afghan rulers as well as earlier dynasties, reflecting their strategic acumen and architectural prowess. These forts, including Rohtasgarh, were strategically positioned to control key trade routes and demonstrate advanced military architecture. The robust construction and strategic placements of these forts highlight the region's historical importance in both medieval Indian history and earlier periods.

Rohtasgarh Fort:

Figure 6. Aerial view of Rohtasgarh Fort atop the lush green hills of the Kaimur Range. (Photo credit: Rohtas Administration)

Introduction

Rohtasgarh Fort (Kuraishi, 1931), perched atop a steep hill in Bihar's Kaimur Range (see [Figure 6](#)), stands as a monument of significant historical and strategic importance. Reflecting its rich

history through its strategic location, mythological associations, and various historical roles, the fort is accessible via a trek from the village of Rohtasgarh in Rohtas District, approximately 80 kilometres from Sasaram, the nearest major town. Visitors typically reach Sasaram by taxi or local transport before embarking on the trek to the fort.

Early History and Mythological Associations

Local legends link Rohtasgarh Fort to Rohitasva, the son of the legendary king Harishchandra. Although historical records are sparse, inscriptions referring to "Mahasamanta Shashanka-dava" suggest a connection to the Gauda king Shashanka. Dating back to the 7th century BCE, the fort is among India's oldest hill forts, with its mythological associations adding to its historical significance.

Medieval Period and Strategic Importance

During the medieval period, Rohtasgarh Fort emerged as a key stronghold under various dynasties, including the Hindu Solar dynasty and later Rajput rulers. Its strategic location allowed it to control vital trade routes and agricultural lands, enhancing its economic and political influence. The fort served as a centre for governance and military operations, reflecting a blend of diverse cultural influences.

Afghan Rule and Architectural Renovations

In the 16th century, Sher Shah Suri, the Afghan emperor, recognized the fort's strategic value and undertook extensive renovations. The construction of the Sher Shah Gate, with its monumental entrance and intricate carvings, exemplifies the fort's enhanced defensive and architectural grandeur under Afghan rule. In 1558 AD, Raja Man Singh, a general under Akbar, enhanced Rohtas Fort with the 'Mahal Sarai' and Persian-style gardens. The Aina Mahal and Baradari (Public Hall) or Deewan-e Aam, added later, reflect further architectural sophistication and beauty.

Cultural Fusion and Architectural Diversity

Rohtasgarh Fort is a testament to cultural fusion, featuring both Hindu temples and mosques from different periods. This architectural diversity underscores the fort as a melting pot of religious and cultural traditions, showcasing a blend of local techniques and external influences. The fort's architecture reflects the craftsmanship and engineering expertise of its various rulers.

Symbol of Resistance and Regional Identity

The fort has long symbolized resistance against foreign invasions and regional identity. Its history is marked by numerous battles and sieges, serving as a testament to the resilience and autonomy of the local population. Rohtasgarh Fort's legacy represents Bihar's historical struggles and cultural heritage.

Maoist Occupation, Conflict, and Liberation

In the late 20th century, Rohtasgarh Fort became a Maoist stronghold due to its strategic location and historical significance. The Maoists used the fort as a base of operations, impacting its condition and accessibility. A pivotal moment came in August 2008 when Vikas Vaibhav, Superintendent of Police, launched the Son Mahotsav community policing initiative to reclaim the Kaimur Hills from insurgents. On January 26, 2009, the fort was liberated through Operation Vidhwansh, marking the end of Maoist control and the beginning of a new era of peace and restoration.

Figure 7. Tricolour Hoisted Post-Maoist Recapture, 26 January, 2009. (Photo Credit: Rohtas Administration)

Following its liberation, the Indian flag was proudly hoisted at Rohtasgarh Fort on Republic Day 2009 (see, symbolizing national pride and the fort's restored significance.

Architectural Description

Rohtasgarh Fort, located in the rough Kaimur Hills, is a prime example of medieval military architecture. Its walls, made from dressed stone blocks and lime mortar, follow the natural shape of the land, enhancing its defensive capabilities. The steep cliffs on three sides act as a strong natural barrier, making the fort difficult for invaders to reach. The fort's defensive walls (Kuraishi, 1931) are reinforced with bastions, loopholes, and machicolations, showcasing advanced military engineering suited to the terrain. The grand Sher Shah Gate, the main entrance, features a large arched gateway flanked by bastions and adorned with intricate carvings, combining ceremonial and defensive elements and highlighting the builders' strategic vision.

Festivals and Cultural Significance

Figure 8. Tribes celebrating Rohtasgarh Mahotsav at Rohtasgarh Fort 2023. (Photo credit: Rohtas Administration)

The Vanvasi Kalyan Mahotsav, also known as the Rohtasgarh Mahotsav, is a vital cultural event held annually on March 5th at Rohtasgarh Fort in the Kaimur Hills. Celebrated by the Oraon tribe, the festival follows the worship of the sacred Karam tree on Magh Purnima (February 16th). This tree symbolizes ancestral connection and cultural heritage for the Oraon people.

For over 15 years, tribes from various parts of India and Nepal have gathered at Rohtasgarh for this pilgrimage, showcasing a powerful display of cultural unity. The festival involves rituals such as taking soil from beneath the Karam tree, signifying the preservation of ancestral ties and spiritual continuity.

This festival not only serves as a religious observance but also as a platform for cultural preservation and education. It emphasizes the importance of maintaining tribal traditions and fosters solidarity among diverse tribal communities. The festival's high-profile support from national and regional figures underscores its significance in preserving and celebrating the rich cultural heritage of the Oraon tribe.

Condition Description and Conservation Status

Rohtasgarh Fort faces significant preservation challenges due to natural weathering, structural degradation, and human activities.

Figure 9. Baradari or the Public Hall (Deewan-e-Aam) at Rohtasgarh Fort: Thomas Daniell's painting (1790 AD) and the current view (2023)

The exposed stone surfaces are particularly susceptible to erosion and damage (see [Figure 9](#)) from environmental factors. Signs of distress include structural instability, cracks, erosion of mortar joints, leaning bastions, and overgrowth of vegetation, which accelerate the fort's deterioration.

Threats and Conservation Status

The fort is threatened by environmental factors, acts of vandalism, and a lack of heritage awareness within the regional community. These issues highlight the urgent need for comprehensive and sustained conservation strategies. Rohtasgarh Fort is listed as a Central Protected Monument and is safeguarded under Act VII of 1904. The Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) oversees its conservation, and while there have been some stabilization and restoration initiatives in collaboration with the state tourism department, more effective strategies and increased funding are crucial for addressing these threats and ensuring the fort's preservation and historical significance.

Shergarh Fort

Introduction

Shergarh Fort ([Kuraishi, 1931](#)), located on the Kaimur hills in Sasaram, Bihar, India, stands as a remarkable example of 16th-century military architecture. Built between 1540 and 1545 CE by the Afghan ruler Sher Shah Suri, the fort exemplifies strategic ingenuity and impressive defensive design.

Figure 10. Shergarh Fort on the bank of the Durgawati River, with lush green valley and fort ruins. (Photo credit: Bihar Tourism)

Perched on a high plateau (see [Figure 10](#)), its visibility is minimized by high surrounding walls and natural defences such as the Durgavati River and dense forests. The fort's sophisticated design includes an extensive network of tunnels and vast cellars capable of accommodating up to 10,000

soldiers. Originally designed as both a defensive stronghold and a residence for Sher Shah Suri and his family, the fort was equipped with facilities to ensure their protection and sustenance.

Early History and Mythological Associations

Shergarh Fort's placement on the Kaimur hills holds both historical and mythological significance. Its concealed position, surrounded by formidable walls and natural barriers, reflects ancient architectural strategies aimed at ensuring security and control. The Kaimur region, with its association to various historical events and local legends, adds to the fort's mystique.

Sher Shah Suri, renowned for his military strategy and administrative reforms, commissioned the fort to secure his reign against potential threats. The fort's design features hidden entrances and a complex network of underground chambers, reflecting Sher Shah's strategic foresight. These underground spaces, including tunnels and large cellars, played a critical role in defence and logistical support.

The fort's hidden nature, with unexplored tunnels and underground chambers, contributes to its legendary status. Historical accounts recount the fort as a site of significant conflict following Sher Shah Suri's death. Mughal Emperor Humayun led an assault on the fort, resulting in the massacre of Sher Shah's family and soldiers. It is reported that the bodies of Sher Shah's family were thrown into the Durgavati River, while many soldiers perished in the fort's tunnels.

Architectural Description

Shergarh Fort is distinguished by its robust defensive architecture. The high, thick walls and strategically placed bastions were designed to offer substantial protection against external threats and maintain control over the surrounding landscape. The fort's elevated position on a plateau further enhanced its defensive capabilities.

Underground Chambers and Tunnels

The fort is renowned for its intricate network of underground chambers and tunnels, which served various purposes including storage, retreats, and as part of the defensive system. Some tunnels remain unexplored, adding to the fort's historical intrigue and strategic significance.

Condition Description and Conservation Status

Shergarh Fort is grappling with severe challenges, including significant structural issues and threats to its preservation. The fort is partially in ruins, with substantial damage (Vaibhav, 2014) to its walls and roofs. Overgrowth of vegetation has exacerbated the deterioration, further compromising the structural integrity of the fort. This long-term neglect has resulted in a lack of repairs and maintenance, leading to accelerated degradation.

Temples

The Kaimur Hills are rich in ancient temples, which illustrate the region's deep-seated religious traditions and architectural styles. These temples, dating back to various historical periods, serve as important cultural and spiritual landmarks, offering insights into the region's historical evolution and its role in ancient religious practices.

Mundeshwari Temple

The Mundeshwari Temple, located on Piwara Hill in Kaimur District, Bihar, is one of the oldest continuously functional Hindu temples in India. Dedicated to Lord Shiva and Goddess Shakti, this ancient site exemplifies early Indian temple architecture. Traditionally, the temple's origins are dated to the 3rd or 4th century CE, though some scholars (Jha, 2011) suggest it may trace back even further, possibly to the 2nd century BCE during the Sunga period.

Historical and Cultural Significance

The Mundeshwari Temple is a prominent pilgrimage site, especially during festivals like Navratri and Shivaratri. It has been in continuous worship since its inception, making it one of India's oldest surviving temples with ongoing rituals.

Figure 11. Thomas and William Daniell's painting (1790 A.D) and the current photograph 2023. (Photo Credit: Bihar Tourism)

During British rule, scholars like Thomas Daniell ([Daniell, 1812](#)) and Francis Buchanan documented ([Buchanan, 1934](#)) the temple's architecture and significance. Daniell's paintings (see [Figure 11](#)) in the late 1700s and Buchanan's writings in the early 1800s played crucial roles in preserving the temple's cultural heritage. Supported by dynasties such as the Guptas, Palas, and Gahadavalas, the temple's inscriptions provide insights into its history, though some have been lost over time.

Architectural Significance

Constructed in the Nagara style, the temple's unique octagonal layout ([Kuraishi, 1931](#)) is rare in Indian architecture. The structure includes a sanctum sanctorum (garbhagriha) and a small mandapa (hall), but the shikhara, or spire, is absent, likely due to invasions or natural decay. Inside the sanctum, the temple houses a revered Chaturmukh (four-faced) Shiva linga alongside Devi Mundeshwari, an incarnation of Goddess Shakti, emphasizing the temple's significance in Shaktism. The temple's walls feature intricate carvings of deities like Ganesha, Vishnu, and Surya, showcasing the artisans' exceptional skill.

Conservation Status

The Mundeshwari Temple is currently maintained by the Bihar State Board of Religious Trust (BSBRT), which oversees religious activities, general cleanliness, and arrangements at the site. Despite these efforts, the temple has not undergone professional conservation by the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI), even though it is a centrally protected monument under

their jurisdiction. This neglect has led to wear and structural cracks, with artifacts suffering from exposure to the elements. There is a pressing need for more rigorous conservation efforts by the ASI to ensure the temple and its surrounding artifacts are adequately protected and preserved for future generations.

Maa Tara Chandi Temple

The Maa Tara Chandi Temple, situated in a natural cave of the Kaimur Hills within the Vindhya Mountain range, is one of the most revered temples in Sasaram, Rohtas District, Bihar, India. Dedicated to Goddess Tara Chandi, this ancient site is steeped in religious significance and historical importance, attracting devotees and scholars alike. The temple is considered one of the 51 Siddha Shakti Peethas in India, where, according to Pauranic legends, the "right eye" (Netra) of Sati is believed to have fallen when Lord Vishnu used his Sudarshan Chakra to sever her body.

Historical and Cultural Significance

The Maa Tara Chandi Temple is not only a prominent pilgrimage site but also a key location in Sasaram's religious history. The temple is deeply rooted in the Shakta tradition of Hinduism, and it is believed that the goddess Durga, in the form of Maa Tara Chandi, resides here. Local legends suggest that when Gautama Buddha, after attaining enlightenment, visited this site, the goddess appeared before him as a young girl, directing him to Sarnath, where he gave his first sermon.

In addition to its religious significance, the Kaimur Hills surrounding the temple offer access to various other attractions in Sasaram, such as the Gupta Mahadev Temple, Parvati Temple, ancient caves, and the waterfalls of Manjhar Kund and Dhua Kund, which have the potential to generate substantial amounts of electricity.

Architectural and Iconographic Significance

The temple's main deity, Maa Tara, is depicted in accordance with the descriptions found in Tantric scriptures and iconography. The idol of Maa Tara features four hands, with the right hands holding a knife and a scissor, and the left hands holding a hood and a lotus. The goddess is portrayed with her left foot forward, resting on a corpse, symbolizing her power over death. The statue, characterized by its short stature, large belly (lambodar), and indigo hue, is adorned with a tiger skin.

The temple complex also houses statues from the late Gupta or later Gupta period, including a statue of Surya and a fragmentary statue of Agni, found outside the temple. These artifacts highlight the temple's ancient origins and its significance in the region's religious practices. A notable feature of the site is the large rock inscription adjacent to the temple, commissioned by Shatrudhan, the son of Kharwar dynasty king Mahanayak Pratap Dhavaldev, in the 12th century. This inscription emphasizes the widespread reverence for Tarachandi Devi during that era.

Conservation Status

The conservation status of the Maa Tara Chandi Temple is fair, largely due to its importance as a major holy site in the area. The temple is well-maintained by the local administration and the state government, ensuring that it remains a significant religious and cultural landmark in the region.

Chaurasan Temple

The Chaurasan Temple, formerly known as the Rohtasan Temple, is a prominent religious and architectural ([Kuraishi, 1931](#)) site located in Rohtasgarh, Rohtas District, Bihar, India.

Figure 12. Chaurasan Temple: Requires 84 stairs to reach the top of the hill. (Photo credit: Aditya Akash)

Perched on a steep (see [Figure 12](#)), conical hillock, the temple commands an impressive view of the surrounding landscape. It is situated approximately 4 kilometers northeast of the Palace and a short distance from Phulwaria Ghat, enhancing its significance as a local landmark.

Historical and Cultural Significance

Historically referred to as the Chauri of Rohitasva by Dr. Buchanan Hamilton, the Chaurasan Temple ([Buchanan, 1934](#)) is deeply embedded in local legends and traditions. According to some accounts, the temple once housed an image of Rohitasva, which was reportedly destroyed by Aurangzeb. However, this narrative is debated, with the more accepted view being that the temple originally served as a Saivite shrine dedicated to Lord Shiva, reflecting its religious importance.

Architectural Significance

Constructed during the Late Medieval period, likely between the 15th and 16th centuries, the Chaurasan Temple is a fine example of the intricate craftsmanship characteristic of Hindu temple architecture from this era. The temple stands on a high terrace supported by arches, which is accessed via a grand staircase featuring 84 steps, thus lending its name "Chaurasan" (meaning 84 in Hindi). The elevated terrace, measuring approximately 59 by 50 feet, was once topped by a dome that has since been lost. This terrace likely served as the site of a mandapa (pillared hall). The sanctum, a square structure with projections on each wall, displays design elements reminiscent of Orissa temple architecture, including bold horizontal mouldings and deep vertical grooves. The façade is richly decorated with carvings of lotus flowers, a small figure of Ganesha, and Dvarapala figures (gatekeepers). Inside, the sanctum measures 13 feet 7 inches square, with an octagonal roof supported by square pillars, and a rough stone is venerated as Shiva's linga. Beneath the grand staircase, several arched chambers may have been used for various purposes, such as storage or ritual activities.

Conservation Status

The Chaurasan Temple is currently maintained by local authorities and the state government. While the temple remains a vital historical and religious site, it faces challenges such as natural weathering and structural wear over time. Despite these challenges, the conservation status of the temple is considered fair. The local administration and state government are committed to preserving and maintaining this important sacred site, ensuring its continued relevance as a historical landmark.

Ganesha Temple

The Ganesha Temple, located near Rohtasgarh Fort ([Kuraishi, 1931](#)) in the Rohtasgarh, Rohtas District, Bihar, India, is a significant religious site dedicated to Lord Ganesha. It is situated

approximately 500 meters near southwest of Rohtasgarh Fort, easily accessible from the fort road, and is in close proximity to other historical sites in the area.

Historical and Cultural Significance

Constructed around the 16th century, the Ganesha Temple holds notable historical and cultural importance. Attributed to Raja Man Singh, who also commissioned the nearby Mahadeva Mandir, the temple reflects traditional Hindu temple architecture. Originally surrounded by an enclosure wall, sections of which are still visible, the temple remains a vital religious site dedicated to Lord Ganesha, a highly venerated deity in Hinduism.

Architectural Significance

The temple features a small sanctum (garbhagriha) and an adjoining mandapa (hall), elevated on a stone platform measuring approximately 34 feet by 38 feet 9 inches. This platform is bordered by a 3 feet 8 inches high plinth with bold horizontal mouldings. The mandapa's exterior has narrow pilasters in low relief, while the interior walls are supported by massive square pilasters. These pilasters uphold twelve pillars, which are square at the base, transitioning to octagonal and circular segments with circular caps beneath cruciform brackets. The mandapa's roof, which was originally conical, has since collapsed. The sanctum, measuring 17 feet 3 inches by 14 feet 6 inches, features horizontal mouldings similar to those at the Rohtasgarh Temple. Its ceiling consists of stone slabs arranged in diminishing squares, with a central boss enclosed in an octagon. Inside the sanctum, a modern statue of Ganesha is placed on a ledge along the west wall, reflecting typical Vaishnavite temple practices.

Conservation Status

Currently, the Ganesha Temple is in a state of ruin, with the mandapa's roof collapsed and signs of weathering and deterioration present. Despite these challenges, the temple's historical and architectural value remains significant. Conservation efforts have been minimal, with the site primarily managed by the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI). The preservation of the temple is essential due to its religious and historical importance.

Afghan & Islamic Architecture & Tombs

The Kaimur Hills are distinguished by their remarkable Afghan-era architecture, characterized by grand mausoleums and intricate tombs. These structures showcase the elegance and complexity of

Indo-Islamic architectural styles. Reflecting the cultural and architectural influences of the Afghan rulers, these tombs represent a significant period in the region's history.

Sher Shah Suri Tomb

The Sher Shah Suri Tomb is situated in Sasaram, Rohtas District, Bihar, India. The tomb is strategically placed in the centre of a sprawling artificial lake that covers 22 acres, enhancing its prominence and creating a serene, reflective environment.

Figure 13. Tomb of Sher Shah Suri in Sasaram - View from the Causeway. (Photo credit: Thrillophilia)

To reach the tomb, visitors cross a wide stone bridge, with access initially guided by the small domed tomb of Sher Shah's concierge located to the north of the lake. This unique positioning underscores the grandeur and symbolic isolation of the tomb (see [Figure 13](#)), reflecting the opulence of Sher Shah Suri's era.

Historical and Cultural Significance

The tomb is the final resting place of Sher Shah Suri, the founder of the Suri Empire, known for his significant contributions to the Indian subcontinent, including the construction of the Grand Trunk Road and major administrative reforms. Sher Shah's reign marked a period of significant change and development, which influenced the subsequent Mughal Empire. The tomb serves as a powerful symbol of his achievements and his impact on Indian history, celebrating his role as a ruler who integrated administrative efficiency with architectural innovation. It remains a site of cultural reverence, reflecting the historical continuity and legacy of the Suri Dynasty.

Architectural Significance

The Sher Shah Suri Tomb is an exemplary representation of Indo-Islamic architecture with distinct Afghan influences. Designed by architect Mir Muhammad Aliwal Khan, the tomb features an octagonal plan, characterized by its grand central dome that rises approximately 22 meters. The architectural style includes intricate stone carvings, inlay work, and ornamental motifs, demonstrating the sophisticated craftsmanship of the period. The tomb is positioned on a square stone plinth and is surrounded by a large artificial lake, adding to its visual impact and creating a dramatic reflection in the water. The design incorporates domed kiosks at each corner, elaborate arched gateways, and remnants of colourful glazed tile work, highlighting the architectural sophistication and grandeur of Sher Shah Suri's mausoleum.

Conservation Status

The Sher Shah Suri Tomb is well-preserved and actively maintained by the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI). The ASI's ongoing conservation efforts focus on preserving the tomb's structural integrity and historical significance. Periodic maintenance has included addressing minor cracks and water damage, as well as enhancing access paths and tourist amenities. The ASI's stewardship ensures that the tomb remains a prominent historical landmark, reflecting its historical and architectural importance. The tomb's condition is monitored regularly, with conservation practices in place to safeguard its lasting legacy.

Tomb of Bakhtiyar Khan

The Tomb of Bakhtiyar Khan is located in Chainpur, Bhabua, Kaimur District, Bihar, India. This site, nestled in a historically rich region, highlights its importance during the medieval period and reflects the architectural and cultural influences of the Afghan era in this area.

Historical and Cultural Significance

Attributed to Bakhtiyar Khan, a prominent Afghan leader and the father of Fateh Khan (who was the son-in-law of Sher Shah Suri), this tomb marks a crucial period in the region's history. Bakhtiyar Khan's influence reflects the broader Afghan impact on the local political and military landscape, highlighting a significant phase in Bihar's historical narrative. The tomb stands as a symbol of the Afghan rulers' architectural and cultural contributions to the Kaimur Hills.

Figure 14. Tomb of Bakhtiyar Khan, Chainpur, Kaimur. (Photo credit: Sayeed Altamash)

Architectural Description

The tomb is an octagonal building (see [Figure 14](#)) with a grand hemispherical dome, situated on a low plinth. It follows an Indo-Islamic architectural style, characterized by its octagonal plan and grand arched gateway on the east wall. The façade features intricate arches, domes, and decorative elements typical of Indo-Islamic architecture. The mausoleum is a two-story structure with an approximate height of 100 to 150 feet. Decorative features include ornate arches, domes, colorful paintings, floral and geometrical motifs, and a shallow chajja running around the veranda, adorned with Quranic inscriptions. Constructed from red sandstone, the building employs traditional masonry techniques, including corbelling for the octagonal interior, arch supports for structural stability, and stone slabs resting on beams for the roof of the chambers. These construction methods reflect meticulous architectural craftsmanship.

Conservation Status

The tomb is a centrally protected monument by the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI). Despite this status, limited efforts have been made to address its conservation needs. The site faces significant challenges, including visible wear and deterioration from age and lack of maintenance. Structural problems such as cracks in the walls and sagging beams are evident, and inscriptions inside the tomb have suffered damage. Overgrown grass, weeds, and the presence of snakes and scorpions further complicate the site's condition. Although repairs were undertaken in 2017, including the restoration of the enclosure wall and the construction of boundary walls, there have been no subsequent conservation efforts. The tomb requires urgent attention to prevent further deterioration and to ensure its preservation.

Waterfalls and Scenic Attractions in Kaimur and Rohtas

In addition to its rich history and culture, the Kaimur Hills, located in the eastern part of the Vindhya Range, are known for their beautiful natural landscapes. The area features lush forests, rolling hills, and impressive waterfalls, known as kund in Hindi, that flow down the rugged terrain. These natural features create a striking backdrop for the region's historic sites and add to its scenic beauty. The varied landscape supports different types of habitats, which helps maintain the area's ecological diversity. This combination of natural beauty and historical importance makes the Kaimur Hills a special and attractive place.

Figure 15. Lush green jungle and mountainous terrain in Kaimur Wildlife Sanctuary. (Photo credit: Bihar Tourism)

Kaimur Wildlife Sanctuary

The Kaimur Wildlife Sanctuary, located in the Kaimur Hills of Bihar, is a sprawling natural reserve that plays a crucial role in preserving both the ecological and cultural heritage of the region. Spanning an extensive area of 1,504.96 km², the sanctuary (India, 2011) is a part of the Kaimur mountain range (see Figure 15), which extends into the Vindhya Range. It was officially notified as a wildlife sanctuary by the Government of Bihar through a notification (S.O. 1160) dated 20th July 1979, under the provisions of the Wild Life (Protection) Act, 1972.

The sanctuary's forests have been home to indigenous tribes such as the Kharwars, Oraon, and Chero since ancient times. These tribes have lived in harmony with the land, contributing to the rich cultural tapestry of the region. The Kaimur Wildlife Sanctuary is renowned for its diverse flora and fauna, which includes several species listed on the IUCN Red Data List.

Notable wildlife in the sanctuary includes leopards, Indian pangolins, sloth bears, hyenas, jackals, wolves, wild boars, chowsingha (four-horned antelope), black bucks, chital, sambar, nilgai, jungle fowl, pythons, muggers, langurs, monkeys, and more than 100 species of birds. The presence of these species, including endangered ones like the leopard, black buck, chinkara, and four-horned antelope, underscores the sanctuary's ecological importance and its critical role in conserving biodiversity.

Figure 16. Telhar Kund and Tutla Bhawani Waterfall in the mountains. (Photo credit: Bihar Tourism)

Waterfall

The Kaimur and Rohtas regions are renowned for their stunning natural landscapes, featuring a range of impressive waterfalls. Telhar Kund (see [Figure 16](#)), situated on the Rohtas Plateau near Bhabua, is known for its picturesque beauty and serene environment, cascading into a tranquil lake. Karakatgarh Waterfall, located in the Chainpur block, blends historical significance with natural splendour, having been a favoured site for Mughal and British officials. Manjhar Kund and Dhuan Kund, near Sasaram, hold cultural and historical importance, with Manjhar Kund associated with Sikh traditions and vibrant local fairs. Tutla Bhawani Waterfall (see [Figure 16](#)), near Tilauthu, offers a dramatic 200-meter drop surrounded by lush green valleys, while Kashish Waterfall, in Amjhore, stands out for its height and historical mentions in the Ain-i-Akbari. Karamchat Waterfall, close to the Karamchat Dam, cascades from 400 to 500 feet and is enhanced by additional falls during the monsoon season. Each of these waterfalls contributes to the region's natural beauty and offers unique opportunities for relaxation and adventure.

Conservation and Preservation Challenges

The Kaimur Hills are home to a wealth of historical sites, many of which are relatively unexplored beyond local interest. These sites, including ancient temples, forts, and tombs, face significant conservation challenges. Four sites are Centrally Protected Monuments by the Archaeological Survey of India (ASI), while others are protected under the Ancient Monuments Preservation Act VII of 1904 in the province of Bihar and Orissa. Despite their protected status, these magnificent sites often remain in poor condition.

For years, the region has been affected by Left-Wing Extremism (LWE), which has made it difficult to carry out conservation efforts. Even after the reduction in LWE activity, there have been minimal efforts to reclaim and properly conserve these sites. Neglect, inadequate maintenance, and access issues persist, with only a few locations, particularly those frequented by devotees, receiving regular attention. Most other sites continue to deteriorate, facing challenges with insufficient preservation efforts and a lack of proper caretaking, further hindering their conservation and public appreciation.

Tourism Potential

The Kaimur Hills offer significant tourism potential with their rich blend of historical, cultural, and natural attractions. Visitors can explore ancient forts, temples, and rock art while enjoying the region's scenic beauty, including lush hills, waterfalls, and wildlife sanctuaries. Strategically

located between the renowned Buddhist circuits of Sarnath and Bodh Gaya, the Kaimur Hills are well-positioned to attract international tourists, particularly those interested in Buddhist heritage and spirituality.

To fully realize this potential, it is crucial to adopt sustainable tourism practices and actively involve local communities. This includes enhancing infrastructure, promoting the region's unique heritage, and improving accessibility. By implementing these measures, the Kaimur Hills could emerge as a distinguished destination, drawing visitors from around the globe while preserving its rich cultural and natural heritage.

Conclusion

The Kaimur Hills embody a diverse and rich heritage that extends well beyond the renowned Buddhist circuit. This region, with its ancient rock art, historic temples, imposing forts, and Islamic architectural sites, offers a broader and more nuanced understanding of Bihar's historical and cultural landscape. The prehistoric rock shelters provide crucial insights into early human life, while the ancient temples and Afghan-era structures reveal the region's deep-rooted spiritual and historical significance.

Additionally, numerous sites within the Kaimur Hills remain undiscovered and await recognition. These hidden gems hold untapped historical significance and have the potential to further enrich our understanding of the region's past.

This paper highlights the importance of recognizing and preserving the Kaimur Hills' hidden heritage. By showcasing its lesser-known but significant sites, we gain a fuller picture of Bihar's rich historical tapestry and underscore the need for continued conservation and appreciation of this unique region. Embracing the Kaimur Hills' diverse heritage will not only enrich our understanding of Bihar's past but also foster greater appreciation for its ongoing legacy.

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